

Broadband spectral characterization of commercial polarization-maintaining fibers

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Abstract: This document contains the results of a comprehensive spectral characterization of nine commercially available PANDA-type polarization-maintaining optical fibers operating in the visible to near-infrared range (450–1750 nm). In contrast to limited manufacturer specifications, which are typically provided for a single wavelength or polarization mode, this work systematically evaluates key fiber parameters across a broad spectral range for both polarizations. The investigated properties include transmission loss, polarization extinction ratio, numerical aperture, and cut-off wavelengths extending beyond the first higher-order mode LP_{11} . The results show good agreement with available manufacturer data while revealing additional spectral dependencies and variations between individual fiber samples. The findings provide essential insights into the spectral behavior of polarization maintaining fibers and support their selection and optimization for advanced applications such as fiber couplers, intermodal converters, or polarization-maintaining fiber-coupled single-photon sources. © 2026 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The goal of this study was to provide a more comprehensive spectral characterization of commercially available polarization-maintaining (PM) fibers, which are typically not disclosed by manufacturers or are provided only for a single wavelength or polarization mode. The investigated fibers were nine PANDA-type fibers with single-mode operation covering the spectral range from visible to near infrared.

The document contains the results of detailed characterization in the spectral range from 450 to 1750 nm. The investigated parameters include transmission loss, polarization extinction ratio (PER), cut-off wavelengths including modes of higher order than the first higher-order mode LP_{11} , and numerical aperture (NA) measured for both symmetry axes and polarization modes. The fibers under test were commercially available PANDA-type fibers from Coherent (previously Nufern) in the standard versions PM460-HP [1], PM630-HP [2] and PM1950 [3], bend-insensitive fibers PM980B-XP [4], PM1300B-XP [5] and PM1550B-XP [6], dispersion compensating fiber PM2000D [7], double clad fiber PM-GDF-6 [8], and a PM2000 [9] fiber provided by Thorlabs which the author suspects is the equivalent of Coherent's PM1950 fiber.

The subsections below provide the measurement methods and results grouped by parameters, offering a comparison of a given parameter for all fibers under test. The reference data is included if provided by the manufacturer. If any further characterization of the fiber has been included in published peer-reviewed papers, these articles are referenced in Section 7. In Fig. 1, all geometrical parameters, polarization axes, and the coordinate system used across this document are marked.

It should be noted that some parameters, e.g., higher-order modes cut-off wavelengths and transmission loss, especially in the longer wavelength range, depend on the local fiber geometry, such as fluctuations in the core and cladding diameters, microbends inscribed inside the fiber during the drawing process, as well as fiber bending and the length of the fiber. Consequently, results for individual fiber pieces may deviate from the exact values given here.

2. Geometrical parameters

The following geometrical parameters were determined based on the scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the fiber cross sections: core diameter across the slow and fast axes, core ellipticity, diameter, and distance between the stress applying parts (SAPs). The estimated measurement error is 0.1 μm . In Table 1, all the measured values are provided together with the reference values published by the manufacturer.

Fig. 1. Scheme of a PANDA-type fiber with marked geometrical parameters, polarization axes and coordination system used across this document.

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of the investigated fibers.

	PM460-HP	PM630-HP	PM980B-XP	PM1300B-XP	PM1550B-XP	PM1950	PM2000	PM2000D	PM-GDF-6
$d_{core\ reference}$ [μm]	3	3.5	5.5	8	8.5	7	-	2.1	6
$d_{core\ x}$ [μm]	2.28	3.32	5.39	7.5	8.25	6.45	6.37	2.31	6.33
$d_{core\ y}$ [μm]	2.75	3.97	6.02	8.19	9.06	7.06	7.06	2.95	6.50
core ellipticity	1.21	1.20	1.12	1.09	1.10	1.10	1.11	1.28	1.03
D_{SAP} [μm]	16.9	18.4	18.7	18.6	19.7	20.2	20.5	27.8	23.6
$d_{SAP\ x}$ [μm]	37.5	35.6	35.9	34.9	36.9	35.7	36.7	35.1	31.9
$d_{SAP\ y}$ [μm]	38.9	36.7	37.9	36.3	38.2	37.9	37.6	36.6	32.3
SAPs ellipticity	1.04	1.03	1.06	1.04	1.04	1.06	1.02	1.04	1.01
$d_{clad\ reference}$ [μm]	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
d_{clad} [μm]	125.4	124.9	125.0	124.2	125.6	124.3	124.8	126.4	126.5

The core dimensions are in good agreement with the diameters provided by the manufacturers. However, what the manufacturers do not disclose is that the cores are noticeably elliptical, with the longer axis of the ellipse parallel to the fast axis of the fiber in all fibers except the PM-GDF-6 fiber. For the PM-GDF-6 fiber, the ellipse is rotated at approximately 20° with respect to the polarization axes. This causes the spatial higher-order modes to have a symmetry axis rotated with respect to the polarization axis, which is described in detail in [10].

Additionally, the PM980B-XP, PM1300B-XP, PM1550B-XP, PM1950, and PM2000 fibers have a noticeable refractive index dip in the center of the core with a sub-micron diameter. This effect is most likely the result of the core center not being fully sealed during the MCVD process of fiber preform development. An example SEM image of the PM1550B-XP fiber, for which the refractive index dip is clearly visible, is shown in Fig. 2.

3. Numerical aperture

The NA of the fibers was measured by registering the mode field distribution with a camera sensor at different distances from the fiber output. The first measurement was always done with the fiber tip touching the camera protective glass, and the last one at a 10 mm distance. The output beam diameters were measured along slow and fast axis at each distance using the $I_{max}/\exp(2)$ criterion, where I_{max} is the intensity of the beam in the maximum of the Gaussian fit of the intensity cross section. By linear fitting of the beam diameters with respect to the distance between the camera and the fiber tip, the divergence angle 2α was determined and used to calculate the NA based on the equation:

$$NA = \sin(\alpha). \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. SEM image of the PM1550B-XP fiber showing a refractive index dip in the center of the core.

To show potential influence of the fiber core's ellipticity onto the NA, the measurement was conducted for both polarization modes and in two cross sections through the mode field (across the x and y directions in Fig. 1). The error of the measurement method was determined to be below 0.01. For most of the fibers the measured values remain the same for both polarizations and beam cross sections, and correspond well to the values provided by the manufacturers. Small variations and deviations were observed for the PM1550B-XP, PM1950, and PM2000 fibers. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. NA of the fibers measured across the slow and fast axis for both polarization fundamental modes. The x and y directions of the cross sections are indicated in Fig. 1.

	PM460-HP	PM630-HP	PM980B-XP	PM1300B-XP	PM1550B-XP	PM1950	PM2000	PM2000D	PM-GDF-6
$NA_{reference}$	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.125	0.20	0.20	0.37	0.18
NA_x^{slow}	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.19	0.19	0.36	0.18
NA_y^{slow}	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.15	0.21	0.20	0.36	0.18
NA_x^{fast}	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.19	0.19	0.36	0.18
NA_y^{fast}	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.21	0.20	0.36	0.18

4. Spectral dependence of the transmission loss

The transmission loss was measured using a cut-back method. The light beam from the supercontinuum NKT Photonics SuperK Compact was focused on the fiber core with a plan apochromatic 20x objective from Mitutoyo. The polarization at the input and output was set to transmission mode (i.e., input polarization matching one eigen polarization mode and the analyzer) with a pair of wire grid broadband polarizers WP25M-UB1 from Thorlabs. The transmission spectra were registered with an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) Yokogawa AQ6374. Firstly, the transmission was measured for a few tens of meters long fiber. In the next step, while ensuring that the excitation conditions remained constant, the fiber was cut to a length of approximately 1 m. The change in the spectra registered before and after cutting the fiber was divided by the change in the fiber length to determine the spectral transmission loss per meter of the fiber. The results are shown in Fig. 3, divided into three sets for visibility purposes. If a reference value was provided by the manufacturer, it is included in the graphs as a point with a color corresponding to the line color. The accuracy of the method was determined to be approximately 0.2 dB/m, which is relatively high compared to the obtained values and is mainly influenced by the ability to achieve consistent focusing of the output beam on the OSA slit and the maximum available length of the fiber before cutting.

For all investigated fibers in the longer wavelength range, the measured losses are higher for fast axis launch, which corresponds to the longer axis of the elliptical core. This effect might be somewhat surprising. In non-PANDA-type elliptical core fibers, the shorter axis usually exhibits higher losses due to geometrically weaker mode confinement. In PANDA fibers with perfectly round cores, the slow axis tends to have higher losses due to stronger slow mode interaction with the stress applying parts. However, if both of these effects are present in

the same fiber, the losses are not simply defined by the shape of the core or the stress, but rather by the overlap of both effects. In this case, the stress rods contribute to higher losses in the shorter wavelength range, where the geometrical effects are still negligible due to the mode diameter being smaller than the core diameter. However, for longer wavelengths, for which the mode area becomes larger than the core, the leakage of the mode along the shorter ellipse axis is confined by the presence of the stress rods. As a result, the longer axis, corresponding to the fast polarization mode, has a larger mode area with less confined mode, and therefore exhibits higher loss in the infrared range.

It is also worth noting that for fibers PM460-HP and PM630-HP, significant bending losses were observed for wavelengths above 500 nm and 900 nm, respectively. Even a large bending radius of 10 cm causes losses of a few tens of dB in this range. Therefore, their recommended operating range is below these wavelengths or up to 660 nm and 990 nm, respectively, for straight pieces of fiber.

Fig. 3. Spectral characteristics of transmission loss. Reference values provided by the manufacturers are marked as points in colors corresponding to the line colors.

5. Polarization extinction ratio

For the PER measurement, the same setup was used as for the measurement of the transmission loss. The rough determination of the fiber slow and fast axes was based on the camera view of the fiber facet at the input and output. For more accurate measurement, first the maximum extinction of the signal was found, and the transmission was determined by rotating the analyzer axis by 90° from that azimuth. The difference between the extinction and transmission spectra resulted in the spectral dependence of PER. The results are shown in Fig. 4, again grouped into three sets of three fibers for visibility purposes.

For all fibers except PM2000D, the PER measured for a few tens of meters long fiber is comparable to the PER measured for a 1 m long fiber. For the PM2000D, however, the PER strongly degrades with increasing fiber length. The manufacturer promises a minimum of 20 dB normalized crosstalk at 1550 nm for a 2 m long piece of this fiber, which is in agreement with the result obtained for a 1 m long fiber in this study, shown in Fig. 4, blue lines in the lowest graph. However, for a few tens of meters of the fiber, the PER drops well below 5 dB at this wavelength. The comparison between a 47 m long fiber and a 1 m long fiber is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Spectral dependence of PER for both polarization modes of all investigated fibers.

Fig. 5. Spectral dependence of PER for both polarization modes for a 47 m and 1 m long pieces of PM2000D fiber.

6. Higher-order modes cut-off wavelengths

The manufacturers of the fibers provide only the first-order mode cut-off wavelength, i.e., the wavelength above which the fiber becomes single-mode. The goal of this study was, among others, to provide cut-off wavelengths for higher-order modes. These wavelengths were determined in one of the two ways: (i) excitation of the core with a tilted or offset beam and observation of the mode field on the camera with different spectral filters, or (ii) with use of a spatial light modulator and the method described in [11]. In Table 3 the results for all the modes possible to determine using these methods in the spectral range from 450 to 1700 nm are included and compared to the cut-off wavelength of the first higher-order mode LP_{11} provided by the manufacturer. The results for PM1550B-XP, PM1950 and PM-GDF-6 fibers were additionally confirmed by numerical simulations based on the geometries retrieved from the SEM images. Some of the results of the numerical simulations are included

in the publications showing the application of these fibers in the generation of nonlinear phenomena [12, 13] and conversion of linearly polarized modes to vortex modes [10, 14]. It should be noted that the cut-off wavelengths of the higher-order modes strongly depend on the local fiber geometry and fiber bending, including microbends inscribed in the fiber during the drawing process. Therefore, these values might differ by up to 100 nm from piece to piece of the same fiber model. The measurements were conducted for approximately 1 m long fibers, for which the cut-off wavelengths might be also longer than for long pieces of fibers.

Table 3. Measured higher-order modes cut-off wavelengths.

	PM460-HP	PM630-HP	PM980B-XP	PM1300B-XP	PM1550B-XP	PM1950	PM2000	PM2000D	PM-GDF-6
$LP_{11reference}$ [nm]	420	570	920	1210	1380	1720	1720	1110	1440
LP_{11} [nm]	<450	560	880	1130	1340	1670	1700	1180	1430
LP_{21} [nm]			600	670	860	1050	1030	710	880
LP_{02} [nm]			530	600	840	940	920	630	720
LP_{31} [nm]				560	650	690	790	510	
LP_{12} [nm]				470	600	650	720		
LP_{41} [nm]					530	620	630		
LP_{03} [nm]						540	560		

7. Other parameters

This section contains references to publications and data sheets showing spectral dependencies of other parameters of the fibers investigated in this study. Additionally, the author measured the chromatic dispersion, as well as the group refractive index for the PM1300B-XP and PM-GDF-6 fibers as a part of her doctoral dissertation. The results are shown in Fig. 6. In the legend of the graph, the LP_{11x} corresponds to the LP_{11} mode split along the x axis, and LP_{11y} to the one split along the y axis shown in Fig. 1; polx corresponds to slow mode and poly to fast mode.

Fig. 6. Spectral dependence of chromatic dispersion D and group refractive index N_{eff} for the PM1300B-XP (left column) and PM-GDF-6 (right column) fibers.

The fiber manufacturer Coherent published a data sheet with chromatic dispersion of the PM460-HP fiber [15]. The author's group published papers showing spectral dependencies of the chromatic dispersion as well as group

refractive index and phase birefringence in the PM1550B-XP fiber [12, 13] for the first two spatial modes and both polarizations, as well as phase birefringence in PM1950 fiber [14] and PM-GDF-6 fiber [10] for the fundamental mode and the first higher-order mode LP₁₁. Three publications show spectral dependencies of the chromatic dispersion of the fundamental mode in the PM2000D fiber [16–18] expressed both in chromatic dispersion units and as group velocity dispersion, without specifying which polarization mode was measured.

8. Conclusions

The goal of this study was to provide spectral characteristics of commercially available PM fibers, covering a broad spectral range especially over the three telecom windows while maintaining single-mode operation. The results are in good agreement with data provided by the fiber manufacturers for a single wavelength. Based on the SEM images it can be concluded that the PM2000 fiber sold by Thorlabs and PM1950 fiber sold by Coherent are the same fiber, which is also confirmed by nearly identical results of all investigated parameters obtained for these two fibers. Therefore, by comparing the results for both fibers, it is also possible to draw conclusions to what extent the fiber parameters are constant from piece to piece of a fiber. The detailed characterization conducted within this study was a necessary step in preparation for the application of the PM fibers in development of PM-fiber-coupled single-photon sources.

Data availability Raw data for all the results shown in this document are available from the author upon request.

Funding This work was supported by the National Science Center of Poland (Narodowe Centrum Nauki) under grant Miniatura 9 (2025/09/X/ST7/00365).

References

1. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM460-HP Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/single-mode/PM460-HP>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
2. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM630-HP Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/single-mode/PM630-HP>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
3. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM1950 Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://coherentinc.my.site.com/Coherent/PM1950>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
4. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM980B-XP Bend-Insensitive Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/single-mode/PM980B-XP>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
5. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM1300B-XP Bend-Insensitive Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/single-mode/PM1300B-XP>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
6. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM1550B-XP Bend-Insensitive Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/single-mode/PM1550B-XP>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
7. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM2000D Dispersion Compensating Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/laser-and-amplifier-fibers/PM2000D>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
8. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *PM-GDF-6 Double-Clad Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/components-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/laser-and-amplifier-fibers/PM-GDF-6-125-M>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
9. Thorlabs Inc., *PM2000 Polarization Maintaining Fiber*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.thorlabs.com/item/PM2000>. [Accessed: 2026-04-01].
10. M. Bernas, K. Zolnaczyk, M. Napiorkowski, G. Statkiewicz-Barabach, and W. Urbanczyk, "Conversion of LP₁₁ modes to vortex modes in a gradually twisted highly birefringent optical fiber," *Opt. Lett.* 46, 4446–4449 (2021).
11. K. Zolnaczyk, M. Szatkowski, J. Masajada, and W. Urbanczyk, "Broadband chromatic dispersion measurements in higher-order modes selectively excited in optical fibers using a spatial light modulator," *Opt. Express* 29, 13256–13268 (2021).
12. S. Majchrowska, K. Zolnaczyk, W. Urbanczyk, and K. Tarnowski, "Multiple intermodal-vectorial four-wave mixing bands generated by selective excitation of orthogonally polarized LP₀₁ and LP₁₁ modes in a birefringent fiber," *Opt. Lett.* 47, 2522–2525 (2022).
13. A. Gawlik, M. Bernaś, K. Zolnaczyk, and K. Tarnowski, "Towards generation of hybrid entangled photon pairs by spectrally overlapping intermodal-vectorial four-wave mixing bands in optical fibers," *Sci Rep.* 15, 45490 (2025).
14. M. Bernas, M. Napiorkowski, K. Zolnaczyk, G. Statkiewicz-Barabach, A. Kiczor, P. Mergo, and W. Urbanczyk, "Fiber-based vortex beam source operating in a broadband or tunable mode," *Opt. Express* 30, 27715–27729 (2022).

15. Coherent Corp. (Nufern), *460-HP Fiber Dispersion Data*, [Online]. Available: <https://www.coherent.com/content/dam/coherent/site/en/resources/application-note/components-and-accessories/specialty-optical-fibers/460-hp-dispersion.pdf>. [Accessed: 2026-04-02].
16. P. Ciačka, A. Rampur, A. Heidt, T. Feurer, and M. Klimczak, "Dispersion measurement of ultra-high numerical aperture fibers covering thulium, holmium, and erbium emission wavelengths," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* 35, 1301–1307 (2018).
17. B. Sierro, P. Hänzi, D. Spangenberg, A. Rampur, and A. M. Heidt, "Reducing the noise of fiber supercontinuum sources to its limits by exploiting cascaded soliton and wave breaking nonlinear dynamics," *Optica* 9, 352–359 (2022).
18. A. Rampur, Y. Stepanenko, G. Stepniewski, T. Kardaś, D. Dobrakowski, D.-M. Spangenberg, T. Feurer, A. Heidt, and M. Klimczak, "Ultra low-noise coherent supercontinuum amplification and compression below 100 fs in an all-fiber polarization-maintaining thulium fiber amplifier," *Opt. Express* 27, 35041–35051 (2019).